

AGU24

Spatial Disaggregation of Rwandan Building Exposure & Vulnerability via Conditional Census-Constrained Clustering (C4) using Earth Observation Data

10-meter Country-wide
2022 Disaggregated Maps
of Roof & Wall Material,
Building Height, and
Macro-Taxonomy Classes

2022 Census Records
at the Sector-level Resolution
(Third Administrative Level Unit)

